

Financial and environmental sustainability in aircraft selection for an airline in Türkiye: The LOPCOW-CRADIS application

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <p>Keywords: Airline Management Financial Sustainability Environmental Sustainability CSR Fleet Planning Aircraft Selection</p> <p>Received: 13 June 2025 Revised: 11 July 2025 Accepted: 29 July 2025</p>	<p>Airline companies make operational, tactical, and strategic decisions just like other profit-seeking businesses. One of the most important strategic decisions for airline companies is fleet planning. Following liberalization, planners in the airline industry were faced with different decision-making techniques. One of the most important topics of this period and the literature is multi-criteria decision-making techniques (MCDM). From the past to the present, airlines making fleet planning decisions have paid little attention to the damage they cause to the environment while considering financial issues. Therefore, the aim of this study is to determine the optimal aircraft for an airline that minimizes both financial and environmental damage. Our economic criteria influencing aircraft selection include maximum seating capacity, range (nm), fuel capacity, price, operational cost, current cost per seat kilometer, current cost per ton, and MTOW. Our emission criteria include fuel consumption, CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, NoX, CO, and SO₂, for a total of 15 criteria. We selected seven alternative aircraft models: A319-100, A320, A321, B737-800, B777, A330-300, and B737-700. The ranking of the aircraft models we have identified was determined by applying the LOPCOW and CRADIS methods. In this context, the criteria we identified using LOPCOW were weighted, and our alternatives were ranked using the CRADIS method. Among the alternatives we ranked using the CRADIS method, the B777 was identified as the most optimal aircraft with the highest Qi ranking.</p>

1. Introduction

Businesses that bring together production factors to meet human needs and produce goods and services make operational, tactical, and strategic decisions in order to continue their operations. Airline companies also make operational, tactical, and strategic decisions to shape their future. Fleet planning decisions made at the strategic level are taken by senior managers based on forecasts of the airline's situation in the coming years. For an airline, planning its aircraft fleet is no different from other planning activities. As with other planning activities, it is fraught with complexity, dilemmas, and uncertainty. Creating a successful fleet plan requires engineering and commercial knowledge, the ability to predict the future, and the decision-maker's intuition (Clark, 2017). There are various factors that influence a successful fleet plan. These factors include

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Cite this article: Alici, A. & Yıldırım, M. (2025). Financial and environmental sustainability in aircraft selection for an airline in Türkiye: The LOPCOW-CRADIS application. *Research in Aviation Management*, 4(2), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16629036>

aircraft economics, partnerships, aircraft performance, finance, market assessment, etc. Furthermore, these factors must be taken into account during the planning stage. Strategic planning is fundamental in bridging the gap between the increasing flexibility of resources and the increasing uncertainty of the market (Dožić & Kalić, 2014). The airline industry entered a period of liberalization in 1978. The competition brought about by liberalization has forced planners in airlines to adopt different decision-making techniques. One of the most important issues during this period was the use of multi-criteria decision-making techniques (MCDM) to ensure the most accurate fleet planning for an airline (İnan, 2019). Following liberalization, the aviation industry has become the fastest-growing mode of transportation among all transportation modes. The increasing total fuel consumption and potential effects of aircraft engine emissions on the global atmosphere have compelled the industry, the scientific community, and international intergovernmental organizations to seek various emission reduction options (Lee et al., 2001). The environmental impacts of aviation on climate change have become increasingly significant over the past 50 years (Mahashabde et al., 2011). There are numerous studies in the literature on the impact of aviation on climate change, the damage it causes to the environment, and the measures taken to address it (Rupcic et al., 2023; Cordina, 2002; Marais et al., 2008). Despite the existence of studies using multi-criteria decision-making techniques to determine the optimal aircraft among various aircraft models, no study has been found that evaluates the environmental impacts of aircraft to determine the optimal aircraft. In this study, the research question was addressed based on this gap identified in the literature, with the aim of addressing this deficiency. Accordingly, the research question was defined as “What is the aircraft that causes the least environmental impact and is the least costly for an airline company?”

2. Conceptual Framework and Literature

Air transport is an integral part of the global transportation system and plays a critical role in economic growth, tourism, international trade, and cultural interaction. However, this sector also faces serious challenges in terms of sustainability due to its high operational costs and environmental impacts. In this context, the conceptual framework is structured around three main axes: the cost structure of air transport aircraft, environmental sustainability, and the use of multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) techniques in the context of aircraft selection.

2.1 Airline Aircraft Costs

Today, the most common cost classification for airlines is that established by the ICAO. According to the ICAO, airline costs are divided into two categories: operating costs and non-operating costs. Operating costs are costs directly related to flight operations. Non-operating costs are costs that are indirectly related to flight operations. There are many factors that affect airline costs, and various variables are used to measure their output. These variables include passenger miles, number of seats offered, number of departures, and number of passengers carried (Yükçü & Fidancı). Airlines operate using many inputs, such as labor, capital, fuel, and various materials. For these reasons, the basic factors determining the supply of air services include ticket prices, fuel and labor costs, airport fees, aircraft and maintenance costs, government regulations, and technological developments. Fuel costs are the largest expense for most airlines and account for approximately 20% to 50% of total operational costs, depending on the type of airline and the time of year (Zhang et al., 2021). According to World Air Transport Statistics (WATS), the three largest cost items for airlines on a global scale are aircraft fuel and oil, depreciation and amortization, and flight crew salaries and expenses. Aviation fuel and oil account for 28.7% of total airline costs, highlighting the decisive impact of fuel prices on operational expenses. Depreciation and amortization account for 9.1% of costs, followed by flight crew salaries and other expenses at 8.6% (ICAO, 2022). Figure 1 shows all operational costs and their distribution ratios.

Figure 1. ICAO 2022

In addition to operational costs, airlines' landing and takeoff costs at airports also vary depending on the technical specifications of the aircraft. Traditionally, airport charges have a simple structure consisting of landing charges determined by maximum takeoff weight (MTOW) and passenger service charges calculated based on the number of passengers (Zagrajek & Hoszman).

Based on ICAO and other literature, the following financial determinants were selected as factors that could be decisive in aircraft selection: aircraft price, fuel consumption, operational costs, current cost per seat kilometer, and current cost per ton.

2.2. Environmental sustainability in the aviation sector

CO2 emissions from the combustion of aviation fuels have increased by 3.6% annually since 1980, which is almost twice the rate of increase in total global CO2 emissions. In addition, the aviation sector currently accounts for 2% of all human-induced emissions (Müller et al., 2018). According to the European Union, aviation emissions account for 13.9% of total transportation emissions (European Commission 2021a). In 2019, 915 million tons of CO2 were emitted into the atmosphere from civil aviation activities. The steps taken by the ICAO (International Civil Aviation Organization) and the EU (European Union) to combat global warming in the aviation sector are the CORSIA and EU ETS programs. These programs aim to reduce CO2 emissions in the aviation sector. Recognizing the importance of aviation emissions, the European Union (EU) established a plan in 2012 requiring all airlines serving EU airports to obtain emission permits under the Emissions Trading System (ETS) (Brueckner & Abreu, 2017). The EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) is a plan to develop a carbon offset mechanism for aviation in line with the EU's 2030 carbon neutrality targets (Pang & Chen, 2023). In addition, Airbus plans to introduce hydrogen-powered aircraft into service by 2035. Boeing has stated that flights powered by 100% biofuel technology will be possible by 2030 (Taşdemir and Aydın, 2021). The International Air Transport Association (IATA), a non-governmental organization, announced five roadmaps in June 2023 that include step-by-step actions to achieve net-zero carbon emissions. These roadmaps aim to achieve net zero by addressing aircraft technology, energy infrastructure, operations, finance, and policy issues. Additionally, these roadmaps are the first detailed assessment to include the fundamental steps necessary to accelerate the transition to net zero carbon emissions by 2050 (IATA, 2024). The aviation industry is implementing various measures to improve fuel efficiency, reduce energy consumption, and control carbon emissions. These measures consist of four main categories: sustainable

aviation fuel (SAF), carbon capture and storage, the development of electric and hydrogen-powered aircraft, and the optimization of infrastructure and operational applications (Xu et al., 2025). Airline companies have developed sustainable implementation plans in their business models. Delta Airlines announced that it aims to be carbon neutral by 2030 and has allocated a budget of \$1 billion for this purpose. Jet Airways and United Airlines have also set a carbon neutral target for 2040 (Sharma et al., 2022). In addition, Turkish Airlines plans to have 90% of its fleet composed of new-generation aircraft by 2033, which corresponds to a 15-20% reduction in carbon emissions compared to older aircraft (THY, 2025).

2.3. Emissions from the Aviation Industry

Emissions from aircraft fuel contribute to climate change by causing atmospheric warming (Jardine, 2005). Aviation emissions can be classified primarily as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), nitrogen oxide (NO_x), and carbon monoxide (CO). Over a 100-year timeframe, nitrous oxide (N₂O) has a global warming potential 273 times that of carbon dioxide (CO₂), while methane (CH₄) has a global warming potential 30 times that of CO₂ (Tong et al., 2023). Although the total mass of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) emitted by aircraft is relatively small compared to other sources, it is recognized that the altitude at which they are emitted is significant in terms of their impact on the atmosphere (Gardner et al., 1997).

2.3.1. Carbon Dioxide (CO₂)

Carbon dioxide is a greenhouse gas that alters the balance of radiation coming from and leaving the Earth's surface, contributing to the warming of the atmosphere. Carbon dioxide emissions from aviation have the same effect on the climate as terrestrial emissions from power plants, industry, or transportation sources. Carbon dioxide has an atmospheric lifetime of up to 200 years, so it mixes well in the lower atmosphere over this time period, regardless of where it is emitted (Jardine, 2005).

2.3.2. Methane (CH₄)

CH₄ is also a greenhouse gas. The direct contribution of aircraft emissions to methane is negligible, but increases in NO_x in the upper troposphere indirectly lead to a decrease in CH₄. Additional NO_x from aircraft enhances the CO oxidation cycle, which in turn causes local increases in OH (hydroxyl radical) radicals (Schumann, 2002).

2.3.3. Nitrous Oxide (N₂O)

Nitrous oxide (N₂O), a global greenhouse gas, contributes approximately 5% to the overall greenhouse effect and has a warming potential more than 300 times that of carbon dioxide (CO₂) (Chen et al., 2025). One of the largest sources of this greenhouse gas produced as a result of human activities is the combustion of fossil fuels used in transportation (Beijing, 2006).

2.3.4. Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x)

According to the US Department of Energy, National Energy Technology Laboratory (n.d.), NO_x is one of the most important factors in the formation of ground-level ozone and causes serious respiratory problems. NO_x contributes to the formation of acid rain along with sulfur oxides (SO_x) and causes various environmental problems. Subsonic air traffic is thought to affect the current state of the atmosphere primarily through NO_x emissions at high altitudes. Over the North Atlantic, approximately 40% of all aviation fuel (on an annual average basis) is burned by aircraft flying above the tropopause, i.e., in the lower stratosphere, with the remainder being consumed in the upper troposphere (Schumann, 1997).

2.3.5. Carbon Monoxide (CO)

Carbon monoxide (CO) is a colorless, odorless, and tasteless gas, which makes it an invisible threat. It is produced by the incomplete combustion of hydrocarbons. Its affinity for hemoglobin molecules is approximately 240 times higher than that of oxygen (O₂). Carbon monoxide is also a greenhouse gas produced by the combustion of aircraft fuel (Reumuth et al., 2019).

The emission values most commonly used in the literature and decisive in aircraft selection from an environmental perspective have been used. These are: carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), nitrogen oxide (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), and sulfur dioxide (SO₂).

2.4. Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) Applications in Aircraft Selection

The AHP, TOPSIS, and their fuzzy derivatives used in studies in the literature are based on expert opinions and are sensitive to decision-maker bias. (Kocakaya et al., 2021) used global fuzzy AHP-TOPSIS methods, which are MCDM techniques, to determine the most suitable aircraft for regional airlines in Turkey as the Embraer ERJ-135, Embraer ERJ-145, ERJ-170, ERJ-175, ERJ-190, ERJ-195, Bombardier CRJ-100/200, Bombardier CRJ-900, and CRJ-700; three main criteria: cost, technical specifications, and safety history; and 10 sub-criteria including purchase cost, seat/km cost, environmental efficiency, required takeoff/landing distance, fuel consumption, maximum takeoff weight/MTOW, total baggage volume, number of seats, accident/incident rate, and technical malfunctions. As a result of the study, it was determined that the SWAM operator with the Bombardier CRJ-100/200 model aircraft and the SWGM operator with the Embraer ERJ-135 model aircraft are the most suitable for regional aviation. (Özaslan et al., 2021) In their study, the authors used the AHP and TOPSIS methods from the MCDM techniques to determine the most suitable piston-engine aircraft in Turkey based on 8 criteria: purchase cost, engine power, range, minimum takeoff distance, landing distance, service ceiling, payload, and speed, without specifying the company and model names of the aircraft. (Özdağoğlu et al., 2022) identified five alternatives for flight schools using the MEREC-based CoCoSo method from among the MCDM techniques: Cessna 172S, Tecnam P2008jc, Piper PA-44 Seinole, Diamond DA42 Twin Star, and Sonaca 200. range, maximum cruise speed, takeoff roll, landing roll, service ceiling, engine power, standard weight, maximum takeoff weight, fuel tank capacity, maximum seat capacity, aviation capability of the engine manufacturer, origin (the country's aviation capability) (Akyurt and Kabadayı, 2020) used fuzzy AHP and fuzzy gray relational analysis methods from multi-criteria decision-making techniques to evaluate four alternatives: B777F, A330-200F, B747-400F, and A310-300F; three main criteria: cost criteria, operational suitability criteria, and time criteria; and 16 sub-criteria: initial purchase cost, maintenance cost, scrap value, spare part cost, financing options, unit fuel cost, range, noise class, type compatibility, airport compatibility, loading capacity, maintenance periods, aircraft door size, flight speed, delivery time, and economic life. (Dožić and Kalić, 2014) conducted a study using the AHP method from the MCDM techniques to evaluate seven alternatives: AT72-500, AT72-600, ERJ-190, Q400 NG, CRJ 700, CRJ 900, and CRJ 1000; and six criteria: seat capacity, price, total baggage, MTOW, payment terms, and current cost per seat mile. The results indicated that the most suitable aircraft was the ATR72-600. (Prabowo and Zagloel, 2022) conducted a study using the fuzzy AHP and TOPSIS methods from the MCDM techniques, evaluating three alternatives: ATR 72-600, ATR 72-500, and Dash 8-Q400; range, MTOW, fuel consumption, takeoff distance, landing distance, payload, aircraft price, direct maintenance cost, fleet prevalence, and population (number of aircraft in use worldwide) to determine that the most suitable cargo aircraft is the Dash 8 Q400.

In the literature, AHP, TOPSIS, and their fuzzy derivatives are generally preferred. However, in this study, the LOPCOW and CRADIS methods, which are more current and rarely used for both weighting and ranking, were preferred to create an original model. In particular, the LOPCOW method differs from classical approaches found in the literature in that it weights criteria objectively based on its own data without requiring expert opinion.

3. Method

Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Techniques (MCDM) structure and solve decision and planning problems involving multiple criteria (Arduldoss et al., 2013). In this study, the LOPCOW and CRADIS techniques from MCDM were used in two stages. In the first stage, the criteria were weighted using the LOPCOW method, which is relatively new in the literature. In the second stage, the alternatives were evaluated using the CRADIS method. Additionally, the criteria used in the study, the sources of the criteria, the preference direction in the normalization process, and the codes are shown in Table 1. Emissions values are per LTO cycle. LTO

includes taxi start, taxi end, takeoff, climb, approach, and landing phases at an altitude of 3,000 feet around airports (IPCC, 1997).

Table 1. Criteria used in the study

Code	Criteria	Direction	Reference
C1	Maximum Seat Capacity	maks.	Airbus,Boeing (n.d)
C2	Range (nm)	maks.	Airbus,Boeing (n.d)
C3	Fuel Capacity (US Gallons)	maks.	Airbus,Boeing (n.d)
C4	Price	min.	Airbus (2011), Boeing (2012)
C5	Fuel Consumption (kg/LTO)	min.	IPCC
C6	Operating Cost (per flight hour)	min.	EUROCONTROL, IATA, (2024)
C7	Current Seat Cost per Mile	min.	EUROCONTROL, IATA, (2024)
C8	Current Cost per Ton	min.	EUROCONTROL, IATA, (2024)
C9	MTOW	min.	Airbus,Boeing (n.d)
C10	CO2	min.	IPCC
C11	CH4	min.	IPCC
C12	N2O	min.	IPCC
C13	Nox	min.	IPCC
C14	CO	min.	IPCC
C15	SO2	min.	IPCC

3.1. LOPCOW Method

(Ecer & Pamucar, 2022) The LOPCOW method developed in 2022 is a criterion weighting technique. This method is unique in that it is not affected by negative values in the initial decision matrix. This allows for weighting to be performed on raw data. The LOPCOW method consists of four basic steps. Step 1: Arranging the decision matrix: The initial matrix is obtained using Equation 1 with m alternatives and n criteria.

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & \dots & x_{1j} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & \dots & x_{mj} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \tag{1}$$

Step 2: Values are normalized according to the cost-benefit analysis using Equations 2 and 3.

$$r_{ij} = \frac{x_{mak} - x_{ij}}{x_{mak} - x_{min}} \text{ (cost criterion)} \tag{2}$$

$$r_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - x_{min}}{x_{mak} - x_{min}} \text{ (utility criterion)} \tag{3}$$

Step 3: Using Equation 4, a percentage value (PV) is obtained for each criterion.

$$PV_{ij} = \left| \ln \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^m r_{ij}^2}{m}} \right| \times 100 \tag{4}$$

Step 4: Criteria weights are obtained using Equation 5.

$$\frac{PV_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m PV_{ij}} \tag{5}$$

3.2. CRADIS

The CRADIS method was developed by Puška et al. (2022) as a combination of the ARAS, MARCOS, and TOPSIS methods to identify deviations from ideal and anti-ideal solutions. The CRADIS method consists of eight basic steps. These steps are as follows:

Step 1: The initial decision matrix is created using Equation 6.

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \cdots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \cdots & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \cdots & x_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Step 2: Values are normalized according to the cost-benefit analysis using equations 7 and 8.

$$n_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{x_{jmak}} \quad (\text{cost criterion}) \quad (7)$$

$$n_{ij} = \frac{x_{jmin}}{x_{ij}} \quad (\text{utility criterion}) \quad (8)$$

Step 3: Equality 9 assistance is used to obtain a weighted normalized decision matrix.

$$v_{ij} = n_{ij} * w_{ij} \quad (9)$$

Step 4: The ideal value (t_i) represented in Equation 10 indicates the largest v_{ij} value in the weighted normalized decision matrix, while the anti-ideal value (t_{ai}) in Equation 11 indicates the smallest v_{ij} value in the weighted normalized decision matrix.

$$t_i = \max v_{ij} \quad (10)$$

$$t_{ai} = \min v_{ij} \quad (11)$$

Step 5: Detecting deviations from ideal (d^+) and negative ideal (d^-) solutions using equations 12 and 13.

$$d^+ = t_i - v_{ij} \quad (12)$$

$$d^- = v_{ij} - t_{ai} \quad (13)$$

Step 6: Using Equations 14 and 15, the deviations of the alternatives from the ideal (s_i^+) and s_i^-) anti-ideal solutions are determined.

$$s_i^+ = \sum_{j=1}^n d^+ \quad (14)$$

$$s_i^- = \sum_{j=1}^n d^- \quad (15)$$

Step 7: Using Equations 16 and 17, the value of s_0^+ represents the optimal alternative with the smallest deviation from the ideal solution. The value of s_0^- represents the optimal alternative with the largest deviation from the anti-ideal solution.

$$K_i^+ = \frac{s_0^+}{s_0^-} \quad (16)$$

$$K_i^- = \frac{s_0^-}{s_0^+} \quad (17)$$

Step 8: Using Equality 18, Q_i is obtained, which shows the ranking numbers of the alternatives. The highest Q_i value obtained indicates the best alternative.

$$Q_i = \frac{K_i^+ + K_i^-}{2} \quad (18)$$

4. Findings

4.1 LOPCOW Application

In the first stage, the criteria are weighted using the LOPCOW method. The initial decision matrix created using Equation 1 is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Initial Decisions Matrix

Aircraft	Seat	Range (nm)	Fuel Capacity (US Gallons)	Price	Fuel Consumption	Operational Cost	Current seat km cost per	Current Ton Per Cost	MTOW (LTO/KG)	CO2 (LTO/KG)	CH4 (LTO/KG)	N2O (LTO/KG)	NOx (LTO/KG)	CO (LTO/KG)	SO2 (LTO/KG)
A319-100	132	4256	8.529	92,3	730	4829	3,6	36,92	64.000	2310	0,06	0,1	8,73	6,35	0,73
A320	159	3790	8.498	101	770	4829	3,6	36,92	73.500	2440	0,06	0,1	9,01	6,19	0,77
A321	194	3479	6.353	118,3	960	4829	3,6	36,92	89.000	3020	0,14	0,1	16,72	7,55	0,96
B737-800	189	3377	6.875	106,1	880	4337	3,76	33,11	70.534	2780	0,07	0,1	12,3	7,07	0,88
B777	440	8865	47.890	306,6	2560	9507	3,53	22,07	347.814	8100	0,07	0,3	52,81	12,76	2,56
A330-300	292	6350	36.744	264,2	2230	7827	3,61	22,18	212.000	7050	0,13	0,2	35,57	16,2	2,23
B737-700	149	3440	6.875	89,1	780	4337	3,76	33,11	60.328	2460	0,09	0,1	9,12	8	0,78

In the initial decision matrix obtained, the criteria were normalized using equation 2-3 and are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Normalized Decision Matrix

Alternatifler	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15
A1	1,00	0,84	0,95	0,99	1,00	0,90	0,70	0,00	0,99	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,22	1,20	1,00
A2	0,91	0,92	0,95	0,95	0,98	0,90	0,70	0,00	0,95	0,98	1,00	1,00	1,21	1,22	0,83
A3	0,80	0,98	1,00	0,87	0,87	0,90	0,70	0,00	0,90	0,88	0,00	1,00	1,00	1,05	0,00
A4	0,81	1,00	0,99	0,92	0,92	1,00	0,00	0,26	0,96	0,92	0,88	1,00	1,12	1,11	0,35
A5	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,00	1,00	0,00	0,00	0,88	0,00	0,00	0,42	-6,96
A6	0,48	0,46	0,27	0,19	0,18	0,32	0,65	0,99	0,47	0,18	0,13	0,50	0,48	0,00	-5,52
A7	0,94	0,99	0,99	1,00	0,97	1,00	0,00	0,26	1,00	0,97	0,63	1,00	1,21	1,00	0,78
std.p	0,33	0,35	0,39	0,39	0,39	0,37	0,35	0,42	0,35	0,39	0,39	0,36	0,44	0,43	3,12
Alternatif sayıs(m)	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7

Equations 4 and 5 were applied to the normalized decision matrix obtained, and the results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Standard Deviation, Percentile Values, and Weight Values

Alternatifler	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15
A1	1,00	0,71	0,90	0,97	1,00	0,82	0,48	0,00	0,97	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,49	1,44	1,00
A2	0,83	0,86	0,90	0,89	0,96	0,82	0,48	0,00	0,91	0,96	1,00	1,00	1,47	1,49	0,68
A3	0,64	0,96	1,00	0,75	0,76	0,82	0,48	0,00	0,81	0,77	0,00	1,00	1,00	1,11	0,00
A4	0,66	1,00	0,98	0,85	0,84	1,00	0,00	0,07	0,93	0,84	0,77	1,00	1,26	1,24	0,12
A5	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,00	1,00	0,00	0,00	0,77	0,00	0,00	0,18	48,39
A6	0,23	0,21	0,07	0,04	0,03	0,11	0,43	0,99	0,22	0,03	0,02	0,25	0,23	0,00	30,49
A7	0,89	0,98	0,98	1,00	0,95	1,00	0,00	0,07	1,00	0,95	0,39	1,00	1,47	1,00	0,61
Total	4,26	4,71	4,82	4,50	4,54	4,56	2,88	2,12	4,85	4,55	3,94	5,25	6,92	6,46	81,30
Total/m	0,61	0,67	0,69	0,64	0,65	0,65	0,41	0,30	0,69	0,65	0,56	0,75	0,99	0,92	11,61
Square root	0,78	0,82	0,83	0,80	0,81	0,81	0,64	0,55	0,83	0,81	0,75	0,87	0,99	0,96	3,41
Square root/std.dev.	2,37	2,34	2,15	2,07	2,05	2,21	1,81	1,32	2,36	2,05	1,94	2,38	2,27	2,23	1,09
Pvij	86,44	85,11	76,37	72,63	71,84	79,31	59,24	27,56	85,99	71,91	66,34	86,62	81,87	80,10	8,68
Wj	0,08	0,08	0,07	0,07	0,07	0,08	0,06	0,03	0,08	0,07	0,06	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,01
Rank	2	4	8	9	11	7	13	14	3	10	12	1	5	6	15

4.2 CRADIS Application

In this section of our study, we will rank our alternatives using the criterion weights we obtained with LOPCOW. Table 5 was created with the help of Equations 7 and 8 and is presented below.

Table 5. Normalized Decision Matrix (CRADIS)

Ağırlık (wij)	0,0831	0,0818	0,0734	0,0698	0,0691	0,0763	0,0570	0,0265	0,0827	0,0691	0,0638	0,0833	0,0787	0,0770	0,0083
Alternatif	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15
A1	0,30	0,48	0,18	1,04	1,00	1,11	1,02	1,67	1,06	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,52	0,79	1,00
A2	0,36	0,43	0,18	1,13	1,05	1,11	1,02	1,67	1,22	1,06	1,00	1,00	0,54	0,77	1,05
A3	0,44	0,39	0,13	1,33	1,32	1,11	1,02	1,67	1,48	1,31	2,33	1,00	1,00	0,94	1,32
A4	0,43	0,38	0,14	1,19	1,21	1,00	1,07	1,50	1,17	1,20	1,17	1,00	0,74	0,88	1,21
A5	1,00	1,00	1,00	3,44	3,51	2,19	1,00	1,00	5,77	3,51	1,17	3,00	3,16	1,60	3,51
A6	0,66	0,72	0,77	2,97	3,05	1,80	1,02	1,00	3,51	3,05	2,17	2,00	2,13	2,03	3,05
A7	0,34	0,39	0,14	1,00	1,07	1,00	1,07	1,50	1,00	1,06	1,50	1,00	0,55	1,00	1,07

The normalized decision matrix was multiplied by the criterion weights obtained with LOPCOW as specified in equation 9 to obtain the weighted normalized decision matrix, which is presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix

Alternatifler	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15
A1	0,0249	0,0393	0,0131	0,0723	0,0691	0,0849	0,0581	0,0443	0,0877	0,0691	0,0638	0,0833	0,0411	0,0611	0,0083
A2	0,0300	0,0350	0,0130	0,0792	0,0729	0,0849	0,0581	0,0443	0,1007	0,0730	0,0638	0,0833	0,0424	0,0596	0,0088
A3	0,0366	0,0321	0,0097	0,0927	0,0908	0,0849	0,0581	0,0443	0,1220	0,0904	0,1488	0,0833	0,0787	0,0727	0,0110
A4	0,0357	0,0312	0,0105	0,0832	0,0833	0,0763	0,0607	0,0398	0,0967	0,0832	0,0744	0,0833	0,0579	0,0681	0,0101
A5	0,0831	0,0818	0,0734	0,2403	0,2423	0,1672	0,0570	0,0265	0,4767	0,2424	0,0744	0,2499	0,2486	0,1228	0,0293
A6	0,0552	0,0586	0,0563	0,2071	0,2110	0,1376	0,0583	0,0266	0,2906	0,2110	0,1382	0,1666	0,1675	0,1560	0,0255
A7	0,0281	0,0318	0,0105	0,0698	0,0738	0,0763	0,0607	0,0398	0,0827	0,0736	0,0957	0,0833	0,0429	0,0770	0,0089

Finally, the final result was determined by applying CRADIS stages 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16, our alternatives were ranked and presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Ranking Alternatives

Aircrafts	Ki+	Ki-	Qi	Rank
A319-100	0,7276	0,2874	0,5075	7
A320	0,7309	0,2992	0,5150	6
A321	0,7557	0,3848	0,5703	3
B737-800	0,7362	0,3178	0,5270	4
B777	0,9727	0,9467	0,9597	1
A330-300	0,8884	0,7608	0,8246	2
B737-700	0,7316	0,3016	0,5166	5

All of the above procedures were applied separately for all criteria, and the results obtained are presented in Table 8. According to the table, our alternatives were determined to be B777, A330-300, A321, B737-800, B737-700, A320, and A319-100, respectively, in order of best alternative.

5. Conclusion

This study aims to evaluate the environmental impacts and financial factors of fleet planning, which is of strategic importance for airlines. Our study examines the current state of the airline industry in terms of environmental sustainability and its harmful effects on the environment within a conceptual framework. The literature addresses the main greenhouse gases emitted by the airline industry, including CO₂ (carbon dioxide), CH₄ (methane), N₂O (nitrous oxide), NO_x (nitrogen oxide), CO (carbon monoxide), SO₂ (sulfur dioxide), and the environmental damage caused by these gases. Additionally, policies developed by supranational organizations to achieve net-zero emissions in the future, carbon offset programs, sustainable aviation fuels (SAF), and new-generation aircraft technologies are also discussed within a conceptual framework. Although there are many studies in the literature on aircraft selection using multi-criteria decision-making techniques (MCDM), no study has been found where environmental impacts are highlighted as a decisive criterion. This study aims to fill the aforementioned gap in the literature by providing a comprehensive assessment that takes into account both environmental sustainability and operating costs. Based on the findings, alternatives were ranked using the LOPCOW and CRADIS methods from the LCA

techniques to determine the aircraft that causes the least environmental damage and is also the most financially viable for airlines. Seven alternatives were considered: A319-100, A320, A321, B737-800, B777, A330-300, and B737-700; 15 criteria were identified: price, maximum seat capacity, range, fuel consumption, fuel capacity, operational cost, current cost per seat kilometer, current cost per ton, maximum takeoff weight (MTOW), CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, NoX, CO, and SO₂. The criteria were weighted using LOPCOW and the alternatives were ranked using CRADIS. The most important factor in using this method is that the criteria can be self-weighted without expert opinion.

As a result, our alternatives were determined to be, in order, the B777, A330-300, A321, B737-800, B737-700, A320, and A319-100. Aircraft are generally divided into two basic categories: wide-body and narrow-body. In this study, wide-body aircraft are ranked higher, while narrow-body aircraft are ranked lower. Although wide-body aircraft appear to be at a disadvantage in terms of high fuel consumption and environmental impact per aircraft, their high passenger capacity means that their environmental impact per passenger is lower. Additionally, the economic contribution these aircraft provide to airlines is generally higher. This highlights that unit costs are more decisive than total costs in fleet planning. Although larger aircraft may seem more expensive and consume more fuel, their high passenger capacity and efficient range result in lower costs per passenger. This makes them financially more sustainable in the long term. Therefore, in markets where high occupancy rates can be achieved, wide-body aircraft (particularly the B777 and A330-300) will be advantageous in terms of return on investment.

This study demonstrates that environmental and financial sustainability are not opposing but complementary elements in fleet planning. Multi-criteria analyses conducted using the right methods contribute to reducing both environmental impact and cost pressures in selecting the optimal aircraft type. In this context, the goal of creating a “green, efficient, and profitable fleet” for airlines is no longer just a vision but a mandatory strategic direction.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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